

Kinase independent inhibition of NF κ B transcriptional activity by GRK5 through I κ B α stabilization.

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Members of the G protein receptor kinase (GRK) family that regulates receptor desensitization and members of the nuclear transcription factors family NF κ B have been recently and convincingly demonstrated to interact, although the effects on transcription and gene expression have not yet been described. Using overexpression, knockdown (small interfering RNA) and mutagenesis experiments, we demonstrate that GRK5 couples to and stabilizes the NF κ B inhibitor I κ B α , and inhibits NF κ B activity. Studies with minigenes suggest that the N-terminal Regulation of G protein Signaling (RGS) homology (RH) domain confers GRK5 such ability. GRK5-RH domain overexpression affects NF κ B dependent phenotypes, such as apoptosis protection, cytokine production and inflammation and tissue regeneration. Our results reveal a novel, unexpected role of GRK5 in NF κ B transcription activity regulation that represents a possible target for diagnostic and therapeutics.

INTRODUCTION

G protein coupled receptor (GPCR) kinases, GRKs, constitute a large family of serine/threonine protein kinases that regulates GPCRs signalling¹⁻³. GRKs phosphorylate agonist occupied GPCRs enhancing receptor affinity for β -arrestin 1 and 2 which suppress further inactivation between receptor and G proteins⁴, initiate clathrin-mediated endocytosis of phosphorylated receptors and can act as scaffolds to promote G protein independent intracellular signalling pathways^{2,5-7}. The GRK family consists of seven isoforms that share structural and functional similarities⁸. A central catalytic domain is flanked by an amino terminus domain that includes a region of homology to regulators of G protein signalling (RH) proteins and a carboxy terminal domain of variable length^{9,10}. GRKs kinase domain is relatively well conserved among the different subfamilies (~ 45% sequence identity), whereas N-terminal-RH domains display weak homology (~ 27%) and C-termini have little or no sequence homology. GRKs have different tissue distribution, subcellular localization and kinase activity regulation^{11,12}. Since GRKs modulate receptor signalling, by inducing desensitization, their cellular localization is mostly believed at the plasma membrane, although GRKs shuttle within the cell². Recently, Johnson et al. demonstrated that GRK4, 5 and 6, but not other GRKs, can localize in the nucleus, probably through a functional nuclear localization sequence (NLS)¹¹. This evidence suggests a nuclear effect for the GRK4-6 subfamily and potentially novel roles for the GRKs in cellular function, beside receptor desensitization.

NF κ B is an ubiquitously expressed and highly regulated dimeric transcription factor³. It plays a central role in regulating the expression of genes responsible for innate and adaptative immunity, stress responses, apoptosis, cell proliferation and differentiation¹³⁻¹⁸. Its regulation is tightly associated to its subcellular localization, as it is controlled by the inhibitory proteins I κ Bs, mostly I κ B α . The NF κ B/I κ B α complex sits out the nucleus. Extracellular stimuli, such as tumor necrosis factor α (TNF α) or lipopolisaccharide (LPS), lead to the activation of the I κ B kinase (IKK), which phosphorylates I κ B α causing its subsequent degradation by the proteasome¹⁹. NF κ B is therefore

free to shuttle into the nucleus and to bind specific sequences in the promoter or enhancer regions of target genes¹⁵. This paradigm has been challenged by some recent observation that include in the picture a larger number of partners for the NFκB/IκBα complex. It has been described that NFκB/IκBα is actively exported from the nucleus by means of a nuclear transporter which reads a consensus nuclear exporting sequence (NES) on the N-terminus of IκBα, suggesting that the NFκB/IκBα shuttle continuously between the cytosol and the nucleus^{1,3}. A further interaction has been described between NFκB/IκBα and βarrestin 2, which causes accumulation within cytosol and blockade of NFκB transcriptional activity^{20,21}. All together these novel findings propose mechanisms of regulation of NFκB activity based on macrocomplexes formation and subcellular localization. In several cell types, NFκB drives VEGF, bFGF, IL-8 and other cytokines expression²². In the endothelium, cytokine production sustains a pivotal role in tissues regeneration, by providing the start to neoangiogenesis and therefore blood and nutrient support. Failure to NFκB activation associates with impaired cytokine production and angiogenesis in response to ischemia and wound healing^{23,24}.

On the basis of the flock of pre-existing observations outlined above, we hypothesized that GRK5 regulates NFκB transcription activity. We tested our hypothesis *in vitro* in endothelial cells and *in vivo* in the ischemic hindlimb and in the wound healing processes of the skin in the rat, to study the effects on post ischemia angiogenic responses.

RESULTS

GRK5 directly interacts with I κ B α

To identify the role of GRK5 on NF κ B signalling regulation in endothelium, we evaluated its ability to interact with I κ B α , since it is the main and most studied regulator of NF κ B activity²⁵. In bovine aorta endothelial cell (BAEC) extracts, GRK5 is detected in immunoprecipitates of both I κ B α and NF κ B, suggesting that GRK5 can interact with I κ B α /NF κ B complex (Fig. 1A). In resting cells I κ B α is notoriously linked to NF κ B; to rule out the possibility that the I κ B α -GRK5 interaction is mediated by NF κ B, we explored the ability of GRK5 to bind I κ B α directly. To this aim, we used purified GRK5, GRK2, MEK-I and I κ B α proteins for a binding assay; MEK I was chosen among the available purified kinases because it is structurally distant from the GRKs. As to GRK2, we analyzed its ability to interact with I κ B α , since both GRK2 and GRK5 are considered prototypes of different GRK's subfamilies for important structural dissimilarities in the carboxyl terminus. Both GRK5 and GRK2 co-immunoprecipitate with I κ B α (Fig 1B), while MEK-I doesn't interact, indicating specific affinity between GRKs and I κ B α . Further confirmation of the direct interaction was obtained in an overlay assay (Supplementary Fig. S1) showing that GRK5 interacts with I κ B α with a 5-time larger affinity than GRK2 (GRK2: 0.89 ± 0.09 ; GRK5: 4.78 ± 0.7 densitometric units; $P < 0.05$, ANOVA). This result suggests that the region of interaction between GRKs and I κ B α lies either in the NT region, that comprises the RH domain, or in the catalytic domain, since they both are partially maintained between GRK2 and 5.

GRK5 and I κ B α localize in the nucleus

The next question is whether the effects of such an interaction results in a phosphorylative event on I κ B α . Both purified GRK2 and GRK5 are able to phosphorylate I κ B α *in vitro*, but GRK5 phosphorylation is 2.5 times greater than GRK2's (Supplementary Fig. S2). The biological relevance of the phosphorylation of I κ B α by GRK5 cannot be anticipated by experiments with

purified proteins, and can only be explored in whole cell setups. Therefore, given the aforementioned ability of GRK5 to translocate into the nucleus ¹¹, we evaluated GRK5 nuclear localization by western blot, in BAEC overexpressing the wild type (WT) or the kinase-dead mutant of GRK5 (K215R). GRK5-WT and GRK5-K215R are both found in appreciable amounts in the nucleus (Fig 1C). Of note, both mutants cause an increase in the nuclear accumulation of I κ B α and NF κ B (Fig. 1C). This suggests that the catalytic activity of GRK5 is not required to produce such nuclear accumulation of I κ B α . The interaction appears to be ubiquitous, since also in human HEK293 cells, GRK5-WT overexpression increases I κ B α levels. In this cell type, for which there is available a GRK5 siRNA ²⁶, GRK5 knockdown leads to reduction of the cellular levels of I κ B α (Fig. 1D). Therefore, the physical interaction of GRK5 and I κ B α is needed for I κ B α nuclear accumulation, independently from the kinase activity of GRK5.

GRK5 modulates NF κ B activation

To explore the effects of GRK5 and I κ B α interaction on NF κ B activity regulation we performed a luciferase assay. GRK5-WT and GRK5-K215R overexpression in BAEC significantly inhibits NF κ B transcription activity while GRK2 overexpression has no significant effect (Fig. 1E). GRK5-WT overexpression causes NF κ B transcription inhibition also in HEK293 cells, where GRK5 knockdown by siRNA increases NF κ B activity (Fig. 1F). Since the catalytic integrity of GRK5 is not needed for the effects on NF κ B activity in cells, the physical interaction of I κ B α and GRK5 represents the relevant mechanism of regulation.

RH is the interacting domain of GRK5 with I κ B α

In order to map the I κ B α binding region on GRK5, we created myc/histidine-tagged, truncated mutants of GRK5 including GRK5-WT (1-590 aa) GRK5-NT (1-171 aa), GRK5-RH (51-171 aa) and GRK5-CT (172-590 aa) (Supplementary Fig. S3 and Fig. S4). Transient overexpression in BAEC of GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH, but not -CT, were all able to co-immunoprecipitate I κ B α in

cells (Fig. 2A). These data point to the RH domain as the I κ B α interacting domain of GRK5. Indeed, the overexpression of GRK5-RH decreases the co-immunoprecipitation of I κ B α with GRK5 (Fig. 2B) and therefore competes with endogenous GRK5 in the binding to I κ B α . Hence, we conclude that GRK5-RH contains the interacting domain of GRK5 with I κ B α .

RH is the interacting domain of GRK5 with I κ B α

We examined whether GRK5 domains were able to modulate I κ B α levels by western blot. GRK5-NT and -RH, but not -CT, significantly increase the amount of I κ B α in cell extracts (Supplementary Fig. S5) leading to I κ B α nuclear accumulation (Supplementary Fig. S6). By immunofluorescence analysis in BAEC, we observed that GRK5-WT localizes both at perinuclear and nuclear level, when assessed (Supplementary Fig S7); this compartmentalization is accompanied by a similar subcellular distribution of I κ B α . Also GRK5-NT and -RH co-localized with I κ B α in the nucleus although GRK5-NT and -RH lack the NLS that causes GRK5 nuclear translocation; their ability to enter the nucleus is probably granted through binding to the NF κ B/I κ B α complex. GRK5-CT shows a mainly cytosol localization (Supplementary Fig.S7), and in these cells I κ B α remains mostly in the cytosol. Therefore, by western blot (Fig. 1C) and immunofluorescence (Supplementary Fig S7), GRK5 overexpression causes nuclear accumulation of I κ B α and NF κ B. This nuclear accumulation can be explained by the possibility that the interaction with GRK5-RH masks the NES on I κ B α within the NT region and does not allow active nuclear export of the I κ B α /NF κ B complex³.

GRK5-RH negatively regulates NF κ B activity

To evaluate the effect of GRK5 single domains on the regulation of LPS-induced NF κ B activity we performed a luciferase assay. The overexpression of GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH, but not -CT, significantly inhibits NF κ B transcription of a reporter gene both in resting cells and after LPS stimulation (1 μ g/ml, 4 hours) (Fig. 2C). To further confirm such effect we evaluated NF κ B

transcription activity by EMSA. GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH, but not -CT, overexpression cause a significant inhibition of LPS-induced NFκB DNA binding (Fig. 2D).

GRK5-RH inhibits TNFα transcription

The biological consequences of this novel mechanism of regulation on NFκB were therefore investigated. It is well known that NFκB regulates the expression of many cytokines, including TNFα^{17,24,27}. Since we demonstrated that GRK5-RH inhibits NFκB activation, we explored the ability of GRK5-RH to regulate cytokines expression, in particular TNFα, by means of northern blot. GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH, but not -CT, inhibit TNFα mRNA expression induced by LPS stimulation (Fig. 2E).

GRK5-RH increases apoptosis

Biological implications can be also observed on phenotypes other than cytokine production. Indeed, endothelial NFκB has been implicated in angiogenesis through its protective action of endothelial cells from apoptosis²⁸. NFκB is indeed a critical regulator of apoptotic responses in different physiological and pathological contexts²⁹⁻³¹. The overexpression of GRK5-RH increases cleaved caspase 3 levels, a marker of activated apoptosis (Fig. 3A). Apoptosis is also assessable by fluorescence with fluorescein-conjugated annexin V: cells overexpressing GRK5-RH have a larger fluorescence as compared to control cells (Fig. 3B). Both data are therefore consistent with the acquisition that GRK5-RH-induced NFκB inhibition causes an increase of apoptotic responses.

GRK5-RH inhibits ECs migration and vascular tube formation.

We determined other proangiogenic phenotypes of BAEC that are affected by NFκB. In particular, we evaluated the effects of GRK5-RH on migration of BAECs using a cell monolayer-wounding assay. In presence of Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) 5%, BAECs display a greater capacity over unstimulated cells to migrate into the wounded area. GRK5-RH transfection inhibits FBS induced BAECs migration (Fig. 3C and Supplementary Fig. S8). NFκB promotes endothelial tube formation

on extracellular matrix which *in vitro* correspond to capillary network formation *in vivo*³². GRK5-RH affects this ability as well, by inhibiting vascular network formation on Matrigel matrix (Fig. 3D). Our *in vitro* results build up to the notion that GRK5-RH negatively regulates the proangiogenic responses of BAECs.

AdGRK5-NT inhibits regenerative responses *in vivo*

To extend these observation to the *in vivo* setup, regenerative responses were obtained in rats, by chronic ischemia and wound healing. Chronic ischemia in the rat can be induced by femoral artery removal. We combined this technique with the vascular gene transfer, achieved by means of intra-femoral artery infusion of adenoviruses encoding for GRK5-NT (Ad-GRK5-NT, a kind gift from dr Walter Koch, Thomas Jefferson University) or a control (Ad-Empty). Acute ischemia causes an inflammatory response which causes the formation of new vessels and restoration of blood supply to the ischemic zone. By live digital angiography and TIMI score³³, blood flow is partially restored after 14 days through the AdEmpty ischemic hindlimb (Fig 4A). In Ad-GRK5-NT animals, this adaptative response is greatly impaired with a longer time to ischemic hindlimb perfusion (Fig. 4A). Validation of this result comes from dyed beads recovery from the rat limb muscles, after intra-aortic infusion of dyed agarose beads (Fig. 4B). This impaired response is paralleled by lower NFκB-dependent TNFα expression in the ischemic muscle of the Ad-GRK5-NT treated hindlimb (Fig. 4C). Also, *in vivo*, NFκB activation sustains wound healing by chemokine production such as MCP1 and monocyte and neutrophils infiltration³⁴. We treated blade imposed skin wounds with AdGRK5-NT and observed a longer time for skin healing (Fig 4D) compared to AdEmpty. This impaired response associates with a reduction of monocyte/neutrophil infiltrate (Fig 4E) and lower expression of the chemokine MCP1 (Fig. 4F).

DISCUSSION

To date, GRKs are known as protein kinases that specifically phosphorylate and regulate activated GPCRs, but recent findings unveiled that GRKs are also involved in several interactions with non receptor proteins (PI3K, AKT, MEK), suggesting new cellular functions for these kinases^{20,35-37}.

The present study identifies and characterizes a previously unknown interaction of GRK5 and I κ B α leading to I κ B α accumulation in the cell and NF κ B activity inhibition.

Paramerswaran et al. demonstrated that GRKs RH domain binds p105, a NF κ B precursor, and this binding was stronger for GRK5 than for GRK2 or GRK6³⁸. Our results are in agreement with this finding and expand it to a greater extension since they clarify that I κ B α is the partner of GRK5. We also demonstrated that both GRK5 and GRK2 interact with I κ B α but GRK2 interaction is weaker than GRK5's, and indeed GRK2 has no effects on NF κ B activity. This result is probably due to the weak homology of GRKs in the NT domain that, in presence of elevated amounts, makes GRK2 able to perform the same protein-protein interaction of GRK5. This homology can also explain the result of the Alliance for cell signalling that using a yeast two hybrid screening showed an interaction between GRK2 and NF κ B (<http://www.signalinggateway.org/data/Y2H/cgi-bin/y2h.cgi>).

By cloning truncated forms of GRK5 we identify RH as the GRK5 domain involved in I κ B α binding. Indeed, GRK5-RH overexpression causes I κ B α nuclear accumulation and significantly decreases NF κ B activation and DNA binding, also in presence of LPS stimulation.

Altogether our and previous results point to a protein-protein interaction as the regulatory mechanism for NF κ B activity. Indeed, β -arrestin 2 has been described as a possible inhibitor of NF κ B activity^{4,19,39}, since the direct interaction of β -arrestin 2 with I κ B α protein stabilizes I κ B α levels³⁹. β -arrestin 2 is mostly found in the cytosol, and this explains the finding of Gao et al. showing that β -arrestin 2 overexpression decreased NF κ B nuclear translocation, and blocks the

I κ B α /NF κ B complex in the cytosol²⁰. The results of our study differ from this previous report as we demonstrated that GRK5 enters the nucleus and stabilizes the I κ B α /NF κ B complex. These results suggest that GRK5 and β arrestin 2 regulate I κ B α turnover by different mechanisms in different subcellular compartments. Our results therefore add to the notion that other partners participate to the regulation of NF κ B activity through aggregation in macrocomplexes. Our data point to the nuclear localization of I κ B α /NF κ B complex. This is a much debated issue, since there is not a consensus on the ability of the complex to enter the nucleus. Recently, it has been proposed a dynamic model of the I κ B α /NF κ B complex localization. According to this model, the complex diffuses passively throughout the cell, but it is actively exported from the nucleus through a NES present on the carboxy terminal domain of I κ B α , recognized by the nuclear transporter CRM-1⁴⁰. Our results fits to this model: we found that GRK5-RH binds to I κ B α and prevents the export from the nucleus, possibly by masking the NES on I κ B α to CRM-1, thus leading to nuclear accumulation of the I κ B α /NF κ B complex.

It is interesting to underscore that the kinase capability of GRK5 is not necessary to inhibit NF κ B trascription activity, although it does phosphorylate *in vitro* I κ B α . Indeed, the kinase dead GRK5 mutant was as effective as GRK5-WT to inhibit NF κ B activity. The biological significance of GRK5 phosphorylation of I κ B α remains uncharted.

The regulation of NF κ B activity is pivotal to the expression of cellular genes involved in inflammation responses^{17,24,27} and in various disease like cancer^{22,27,41-45}, cardiovascular disease⁴², diabetes^{46,47}, chronic inflammation^{22,45}. Therefore, interventions aimed at limiting NF κ B activation could be useful in clinical settings. For these reasons, we explored the eventual effects of our *in vitro* results in more complex models. In rats, NF κ B inhibition results in impairment of regenerative responses. In the ischemic hindlimb, indeed, using an adenoviral mediated gene transfer of the RH-encoding GRK5-NT minigene, we observed an impairment of the expected regenerative response.

Indeed, NFκB dependent transcription of TNFα is impaired 48 h after ischemia in the muscle of AdGRK5-NT treated animals. In the same limb, after 14 days we recorded a delay of blood flow recover. These data pair the results of the AdGRK5-NT- treated skin wounds. Also in this model, after 48 h from procedure, we observed an impairment in the production of MCP-1, a NFκB dependent chemokine, and a delay in the wound healing of the AdGRK5-NT treated rats. Our *in vivo* and *in vitro* data are well in agreement to show the negative effect of GRK5-NT on NFκB. On this note, it is interesting to observe that in hypertension, a condition associated with increased vascular levels of GRK5⁴⁸, there is an impairment in neoangiogenesis in response to chronic ischemia³³. Our data open an uncharted territory of exploration for the eventual role of GRK5 in the regulation of NFκB dependent phenotypes *in vivo*.

Given the widespread distribution of GRK5 within the immunological system, it is possible to predict a role of GRK5 beyond angiogenesis and tissue repair. Indeed, in animals with targeted deletion of GRKs, the progression of various acute and chronic inflammatory disorders, including autoimmunity and allergy, is profoundly affected⁴⁹. In a future prospective GRK5-RH induced inhibition of NFκB transcription activity, independently from GPCRs desensitization, may be of physiological and pharmacological relevance in the context of those conditions which recognize an enhanced NFκB as the mechanism of disease.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Cell culture

Endothelial cells from bovine aorta (BAEC) and HEK293 cells were cultured in Dulbecco's minimal essential medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS) at 37°C in 95% air-5%CO₂.

GRK5 gene silencing

The siRNA sequence against human GRK5 and the gene silencing procedure have been described previously⁵⁰.

Plasmid constructs, WesternBlot, nuclear extracts preparation and Immunoprecipitation.

Methods are extensively described in the **data supplement**

Apoptosis analysis

Extracts from cells in basal condition and with overexpression of GRK5-RH were lysed in RIPA/SDS (see data supplement) buffer and analyzed by western blot using anti-cleaved caspase 3 antibody (Cell signalling). Equal amount of proteins were normalized by actin.

In some experiments the detection of apoptosis was analyzed by Annexin-V-labeling using Annexin-V-FLUOS Staining kit (Roche) according to the manufacturer's instruction.

Luciferase assay

BAEC and HEK293 were transfected with plasmid expression vectors coding for a κB-luciferase reporter and β-galactosidase and GRK5 constructs as indicated above. Transient transfection was performed using the Lipofectamine 2000 (Invitrogen) according to manufacturer's instruction. Twenty four hours after transfection, cells were serum starved overnight and stimulated with LPS (1μg/ml) for 4 hours. Lysates were analysed using the luciferase assay system with reporter lysis

buffer from Promega and measured in a β -counter. Relative luciferase activity was normalized against the co-expressed β -galactosidase activity to overcome variations in transfection efficiency between samples.

Immunofluorescence

Cells were grown in chamber slides (Nunc, LabTek) and transfected as indicated above. Twenty-four hours after transfection, cells were fixed with -20°C cold methanol and permeabilized with 0.01% Triton X-100 in PBS. Primary antibodies incubation with anti-GRK5 raised against the amino-terminus region (Santacruz), anti-GRK5 raised against the carboxy-terminus region (Santacruz) and anti- I κ B α (Santacruz) at a 1:100 dilution were performed at room temperature for one hour. Fluorescent labelled secondary antibodies were incubated at room temperature for one hour. Images were taken using an Eclipse E1000 Fluorescence Microscope (Nikon) and acquired using Sigma Scan Pro software (Jandel). Images were optimised for contrast in Adobe Photoshop, but no further manipulations were made.

Electrophoretic mobility shift assay (EMSA)

EMSA was performed using nuclear extracts. Double stranded NF κ B oligonucleotide (5' AGTTGAGGGGACTTTCCCAGGC 3') was end-labeled using [γ - ^{32}P] ATP (GE Healthcare) and T4 polynucleotide kinase (Roche). Samples were subject to electrophoresis in 8% non denaturing polyacrilamide gels with 0.5 % TBE buffer. Digitalized gels autoradiographies were then quantified (Image Quant).

Northern blot

BAEC overexpressing GRK5 single domains were serum starved overnight and stimulated with LPS (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) for four hours. Total RNA was isolated as described. 20 μg of total RNA was electrophoresed and transferred on nylon membrane according to standard procedures.

Hybridization was carried out using Quick Hyb solution (Stratagene). TNF α ³²P-labelled probe sequence was 5' TGCCCTTCCACCCCCTTGTTTCCTCACCCACACCAT 3' (aa 436-470).

Transcript levels were quantified by autoradiography and densitometric analysis was performed using ImageQuant version 5.2. Equal amount loading of RNA was verified by 28S RNA visualization after ethidium bromide staining under UV. In some experiments total RNA was extracted from hindlimbs of GRK5-NT and control rats and TNF α expression was evaluated as described above.

Overlay assay

10 and 20 ng of GRK5, GRK2, MEK1 and I κ B α purified proteins were obtained by a commercial provider (Invitrogen), subjected to SDS-PAGE Electrophoresis by SDS-Page and transferred on nitrocellulose. The membrane was incubated with I κ B α purified protein in binding buffer for 1 hour at RT. Proteins were fixed in 0.5% formaldehyde for 5 minutes and washed with 2% glycine. I κ B α was visualized by chemiluminescence after incubation with the above described anti I κ B α antibody.

Phosphorylation assay

20 ng of purified GRK5, GRK2 were incubated with 20 ng of I κ B α in binding buffer plus 0.1 mM[γ -³²P]ATP for 30 min at 37 °C. Reactions were electrophoresed by SDS page, and the gel was dried and subjected to autoradiography.

Migration and Matrigel Assays

Cellular migration and vascular tube formation were performed as previously described ⁵¹. Extended details are provided in the online data supplement.

***In vivo* Study Design**

To perform gene transfer *in vivo*, we used an adenovirus encoding for the NT of GRK5 (AdGRK5-NT, a kind gift of Walter J. Koch, Jefferson University) and a non-coding adenovirus (AdEmpty).

Animals and Surgical Procedures

Ischemic hindlimbs were generated as described previously³³. Extended details are provided in the online data supplement.

Skin wound healing

We studied 2 groups of healthy WKY rats: AdGRK5NT (n=10) and AdEmpty (n=8) treated. Animals were anesthetized as previously described. After chemical hair removal (Nair, Carter-Wallace, New York, NY) the animals' backs were wiped with 30% isopropyl alcohol. Full-thickness skin wounds (10 mm diameter, 2 mm apart) were made by excising the dorsal skin and panniculus carnosus and the wound was left unrepaired. This standard technique was used in all procedures to ensure that the wounds were created with the same depth.

The wounds were allowed to dry in order to form a scar after the application of pluronic gel (200 μ l) containing AD-GRK5NT or AD-Empty (10^9 pfu). In a subset of rats, animals were euthanized, and wounds were harvested 3 days after wounding. An area of 15 mm in diameter which includes the complete epithelial margins was excised at each time point. A similar amount of skin from the backs of three non-wounded animals was used as a control. Wound tissues were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for paraffin embedding for histology and immunohistochemistry. To monitor the wound-healing process we took digital pictures of the scars at 1, 2, 3, 5, and 7 days after incision.

Histology and Immunocytochemistry

Paraffin embedded, sections were stained for hematoxylin and eosin. Five μ m-thick sections were processed for the triple layered immunocytochemical PAP (peroxidase anti-peroxidase) method. A

goat anti-rat MCP1 (Santa Cruz) diluted 1:250 antiserum was used to localise monocyte-macrophage system cells: In order to reveal the primary antibody, a secondary donkey anti-goat (Calbiochem) antibody diluted 1:100 was used, followed by a goat PAP complex (Calbiochem, 1:100). The peroxidase was revealed in presence of 0,03% hydrogen peroxyde and of an electron donor, 2,5% diaminobenzidine, which becomes visible as a brown precipitate. For negative controls, the primary antiserum was omitted or normal goat serum was used instead of first layer. Sections were then viewed with a Leitz Diaplan microscope provided with a Leica DC200 digital camera.

Statistical Analysis

All values are presented as mean \pm SEM. Two-way ANOVA was performed to compare the different parameters among the different groups. A significance level of $P < 0.05$ was assumed for all statistical evaluations. Statistics were computed with GraphPad Prism Software (San Diego, California).

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

D.S. cloned all constructs, performed western blots, luciferase assays, EMSA, Northern blots, immunofluorescence, migration assays, in vitro angiogenesis. M.C., G.S., A.C., G.G. and F.P. performed in vivo angiographies, animal handlings, blood flow measurements by dye beads, wound healing experiments; G.G.A. and V.C. performed microdissections, histology and immunohistochemistry; D.A and L.P. prepared and purified the adenoviruses; G.I. initiated, designed and guided the study, discussed and wrote the paper together with D.S.; B.T. obtained funds, discussed results and helped writing the paper.

COMPETING INTERESTS STATEMENT

The authors declare no competing interests.

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LEGENDS

FIG. 1: GRK5 binds and stabilizes I κ B α , causing inhibition of NF κ B activity.

(A) Whole BAEC extracts were immunoprecipitated with anti-I κ B α or anti-NF κ B antibodies and protein A/G agarose. After western blot (WB), GRK5, I κ B α and NF κ B were visualized by specific antibodies. (B) Purified I κ B α and GRK5, GRK2 or MEK I proteins were incubated in a binding buffer (as described in Supplement Methods), and then immunoprecipitated and analyzed by WB with specific antibodies. Purified GRK2 and GRK5, but not MEK I, co-immunoprecipitated with I κ B α . (C) BAEC were transiently transfected with either GRK5-WT or the kinase dead mutant GRK5-K215R. Both variants were found in the nucleus together with increased amount of I κ B α and NF κ B. Equal amount of proteins were confirmed by WB for Histone 3. (D). HEK293 transfected with GRK5-WT or GRK5siRNA were analyzed by WB for GRK5 and I κ B α expression. GRK5siRNA caused GRK5 knockdown and I κ B α degradation. Actin is shown for protein loading control. (E). BAEC were transfected with plasmid expression vectors coding for a κ B-luciferase reporter and β -galactosidase together with GRK5-WT, GRK5 K215R and GRK2. Twenty four hours after transfection, luciferase activity was measured and normalized against the co-expressed β -galactosidase activity to overcome variations in transfection efficiency between samples. Overexpression of both GRK5-WT or GRK5-K215R significantly inhibited NF κ B transcription activity, while GRK2 overexpression in BAEC had no significant effect. Data are expressed as mean \pm SE and are representative of three experiments. (* p <0.05) (F) κ B-luciferase activity was assayed also in HEK293 transfected with GRK5-WT or GRK5siRNA. GRK5-WT overexpression caused inhibition of NF κ B activity, while GRK5 knockdown increased NF κ B transcription levels. The data are expressed as mean \pm SE and are representative of three experiments. (* p <0.05).

FIG. 2: The RH domain confers IκB binding capabilities to GRK5 and causes NFκB inhibition.

(A). In lysates from BAEC overexpressing histidine-tagged GRK5-WT, -NT, -RH and -CT, histidine was precipitated using Ni sepharose beads and subjected to WB using anti-IκBα or anti-His antibodies. GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH but not -CT co-precipitated with IκBα. (B). Whole extracts from control and GRK5-RH transfected cells were immunoprecipitated with anti-IκBα antibody and WB was performed using anti-GRK5 antibody. GRK5-RH overexpression attenuated IκBα immunoprecipitation of GRK5. (C) We evaluated GRK5 effects on NFκB activity by luciferase assay, in BAEC overexpressing GRK5 single domains and stimulated with LPS (1μg/ml) for 4 hrs. GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH inhibited LPS-induced NFκB transcriptional activity (* $p < 0.05$ vs control). (D) To further confirm such effect we evaluated LPS induced NFκB binding to DNA by Electrophoretic Mobility Shift Assay (EMSA) in nuclear extracts. GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH but not -CT overexpression caused a significantly inhibition of LPS induced NFκB DNA binding, calculated as percentage of resting cells. Data are expressed as mean±SE (* $p < 0.05$ vs control). (E) The expression of the NFκB dependent cytokine TNFα was assessed by northern blot in BAEC stimulated with LPS for 4 hours. GRK5-WT, -NT and -RH but not -CT inhibited TNFα mRNA expression induced by LPS (* $p < 0.05$ vs control).

FIG.3: GRK5-RH induces BAECs Apoptosis and inhibits cell migration and tubule formation.

(A) To evaluate GRK5-RH effect on apoptosis, we analyzed the cleavage of caspase 3 by WB. The overexpression of GRK5-RH increased cleaved caspase 3 levels, suggesting that NFκB inhibition induced by GRK5-RH caused an increase of apoptotic responses (* $p < 0.05$ vs basal). (B) GRK5-RH overexpression caused apoptosis as shown by Annexin V staining respect to vive cells; propidium

iodide and DAPI were used as cell control ($*p < 0.05$ vs control). **(C)** BAEC migration was measured 12hr after plating using a wounding assay. Migration of confluent BAECs was measured after the cell monolayer was partially wiped away. The area of the migrating cells was measured in several fields of view and is shown in graph. Data are presented as FBS induced percent of migration respect to resting cells ($*p < 0.05$ vs FBS 5%). **(D)** Representative phase contrast photomicrographs are shown of control and GRK5-RH transiently transfected BAEC plated on matrigel. Microscopy revealed numbers of network projections formed in each group after 12 hr of incubation ($*p < 0.05$ vs basal). Data from three experiments in triplicate are summarized in the graph.

FIG.4: AdGRK5-NT inhibits regenerative responses in vivo.

(A) After surgical removal of the femoral artery in rats, blood flow through the ischemic hindlimb is granted by neoangiogenic and vascular regenerative phenomena, mediated in part by NF κ B dependent cytokines. After 14 days of chronic ischemia, the time to perfusion of the ischemic hindlimb was assessed by digital angiographies, showing an increased TIMI score to perfusion in AdGRK5-NT respect to AdEmpty rats ($*p < 0.05$). **(B)** Blood flow was also assessed by muscle content of dyed beads after intrarterial injection in the blood stream. AdGRK5-NT reduced blood perfusion in ischemic hindlimb respect to AdEmpty. Shown is the ischemic to non-ischemic ratio of dyed beads content per mg of hindlimb muscle tissue ($*p < 0.05$ vs AdEmpty). **(C)** RNA from hindlimb of AdEmpty and AdGRK5-NT treated rats was extracted by means of trizol reagent and TNF α expression was evaluated by northern blot. The analysis shows an attenuation of cytokine expression in GRK5-NT treated ischemic compared to AdEmpty ischemic hindlimb. **(D)** In another model of regeneration, the skin wound healing, we observed a longer period of time for healing of those wounds that were treated with AdGRK5-NT rather than AdEmpty at the time of surgery. **(E)** In AdGRK5-NT treated wounds, Hematoxylin/Eosin staining revealed a smaller amount of

infiltrate compared to AdEmpty control. **(F)** Similarly, MCP-1 expression assessed in the wound was reduced by AdGRK5-NT compared to AdEmpty wounds.

A**Histidine precipitation of BAEC lysate**

A

**Rat ischemic hindlimb
Digital Angiography**

B

**Rat ischemic hindlimb
Dyed beads**

